

ISic3560

I.Sicily inscription 3560

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Museo Pepoli (Trapani) ms. 33 and 221

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337224

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) Δ (αίμοσιν)
2. χαῖρε, [π]αροδείτα,
3. ΧΙΡΕΤΕ ΠΟΝΓΕ τεκνίον
4. ἐνθάδε κέτε [— —].
5. θανεῖν πέπρ[ω]ται
6. πᾶσιν.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645635

EDCS 71000781

PHI 337224

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0905

Filippi, A. 2002. Trapani: testimonianze storiche ed archeologiche. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 73-87. At 75 no.14/6

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